

Learner Corpus Approach for Automatic Distractor Generation

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According to (Granger, 2008), language testing is one of the areas of practical application of learner corpora. Automatic question generation (AQG) is one of the rapidly developing Natural Language Processing applications in education - a review of (Kurdi et al., 2020) indicates an increase in number of publications on AQG during recent years and mentions automatic distractor generation (ADG) as one of its most challenging subtasks. However, it is common to rely on pre-defined heuristics in ADG for language testing, while the usability of learner corpus data in this task remains a poorly researched area.

This paper describes a machine learning-based ADG approach (called DisSelector) for corpus-sourced EFL lexical questions derived from REALEC (Vinogradova & Lyashevskaya, 2022) corpus. For each of 3,000 examples of corpus lexical errors a set of candidate distractors was retrieved from other examples with the same correction word, and each candidate was manually labelled as a plausible or implausible distractor. A number of classification models (including classical machine learning algorithms and gradient boosting implementations) were trained on the data. Word and sentence vectors from BERT (Devlin et al., 2019) and Word2Vec (Mikolov et al., 2013) models together with corpus word frequencies were used as input features for the classifiers. The highest F1-score (0.72) in classification experiment was attained by a XGBoost (Chen & Guestrin, 2016) model. DisSelector showed an improvement over the unsupervised baseline during both automatic and manual evaluation.

The scores obtained by DisSelector are expected to increase with the enlargement of labelled training dataset and introduction of new methods of dataset filtering, feature extraction and model training. The plans also include comparing distractors generated by described models with distractors obtained by zero-shot learning technique from large language models, such as ChatGPT and GPT-3 (Brown et al., 2020).

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